

**Supplementary Information for the paper:
How the temperature and size of A cation govern the structure and bandgap of
Zr-based chalcogenide perovskites: Insights from ML accelerated AIMD**

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SI. FORMATION OF DISTORTED PEROVSKITE PHASE FROM CUBIC PHASE

The origin of distorted phase can be traced to its undistorted parent cubic phase as an outcome of symmetry breaking. The transformation from the latter to the DP phase is illustrated in Fig. S1. The transformation happens through an intermediate pseudo-cubic phase, also denoted as tetragonal phase, which retains the structural geometry of the C phase but the internal distortions and the volume resembles closely with the orthorhombic DP phase.

FIG. S1. Schematic graphical representation of the cubic, pseudo-cubic (tetragonal) and orthorhombic DP phase in chalcogenide perovskites viewed in $a - c$ plane (top panel) and $b - c$ plane (bottom panel) respectively. The DP phase is obtained in the setting of C phase by choosing the lattice vectors of the former as follows: $\mathbf{a}' = \mathbf{a}/\sqrt{2}$, $\mathbf{b}' = \mathbf{b}/2$, $\mathbf{c}' = \mathbf{c}/\sqrt{2}$, whereby identity $\mathbf{a}' = \mathbf{b}' = \mathbf{c}'$ holds in the case of undistorted cubic phase. The blue, grey and saffron coloured spheres represent the A, B and X atoms in ABX_3 respectively.

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SII. EFFECTS OF DISPERSION CORRECTIONS

TABLE S1. Lattice constants (a , b and c), cell volume per formula unit (V_1) and band gap (E_g) obtained for DP phases of SrZrS_3 in temperature range 0-1200 K using PBE and PBE+D3 methods. The values in paranthesis are the calculated thermal expansion coefficients as described in section 2.1.

T (K)	Type	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³ /f.u.)	E_g (eV)
0	PBE	7.169 (3.95e-06)	9.829 (1.13e-05)	6.787 (1.76e-05)	119.5 (3.38e-05)	1.225
	PBE+D3	7.121 (5.24e-06)	9.761 (1.29e-05)	6.746 (1.70e-05)	117.2 (3.56e-05)	1.218
300	PBE	7.177 (3.22e-06)	9.868 (1.48e-05)	6.827 (2.18e-05)	120.9 (4.02e-05)	1.150
	PBE+D3	7.131 (4.08e-06)	9.802 (1.46e-05)	6.783 (1.98e-05)	118.5 (3.83e-06)	1.152
	exp [S1]	7.108	9.772	6.741	117.0	
	exp [S2]	7.103	9.758	6.731	116.6	
600	PBE	7.182 (1.31e-06)	9.915 (1.79e-05)	6.876 (2.68e-05)	112.4 (4.62e-05)	1.042
	PBE+D3	7.138 (1.98e-06)	9.846 (1.66e-05)	6.827 (2.36e-05)	119.9 (4.20e-05)	1.032
900	PBE	7.182 (-1.65e-06)	9.973 (2.06e-05)	6.936 (3.22e-05)	124.2 (5.16e-05)	0.886
	PBE+D3	7.139 (-0.09e-06)	9.899 (1.86e-05)	6.879 (2.82e-05)	121.5 (4.65e-05)	0.916
1200	PBE	7.150 (-5.88e-06)	10.037 (2.31e-05)	7.033 (3.86e-05)	126.1 (5.69e-05)	0.778
	PBE+D3	7.133 (-4.92e-06)	9.956 (2.09e-05)	6.942 (3.40e-05)	123.2 (5.22e-05)	0.746
1200 (c)	PBE	7.099	10.031	7.098	126.3	0.732
	PBE+D3	7.041	9.952	7.041	123.3	0.771

FIG. S2. Comparison of time evolution of lengths of scaled lattice vectors $a/\sqrt{2}$, $b/2$ and $c/\sqrt{2}$ of DP/C phase of SrZrS_3 at 1200 K for PBE (left) and PBE+D3 (right) methods. The regions with $a/\sqrt{2} \approx b/2 \approx c/\sqrt{2}$ and $a/\sqrt{2} > b/2 > c/\sqrt{2}$ correspond to the (quasi-)C and DP phases, respectively. Note that averages were run with a block size of 100 points on all data sets presented in this plot in order to make the differences in different regimes of dynamics of the lattice better visible.

SIII. FURTHER INFORMATION ON FACTORS INFLUENCING THE BAND GAP OF DP

In this section, we compare the contribution of atomic orbitals to the band gap of the sulphide and selenide compositions from their respective projected density of states and COHP (crystal orbital Hamilton population). The effect of the charge transfer from A cation to ZrX_3 framework, volume expansion and the distortion of the ideal cubic framework in both systems have been investigated.

In Fig. S3, we observe that upon introducing distortion, there is a clear splitting between mixed d -orbitals anti-bonding states (seen from Fig. S6) between 3-4 eV in the conduction band region, leading to contraction of the energy states in the conduction region which results in further opening of the band gap.

Most of our conclusions remain valid for both the sulphide and selenide systems. The prime difference arises from the X (S, Se) orbital contribution near the Fermi level in the valence region (see Fig. S4). As further elucidated from the COHPs projected to nearest neighbour S-S and Se-Se distances in Fig. S5, the contribution from the anti-bonding orbitals of Se is suppressed by the presence of A cation in $CaZrSe_3$ while the contribution of anti-bonding orbitals from S atoms remain unaffected in case of $SrZrS_3$.

FIG. S3. Partial density of states projected over d -orbitals of Zr atoms a) system i - neutral cubic structure $[ZrX_3]^0$ with no A cation, b) system ii - a hypothetical system $[ZrX_3]^{-2}$ with undistorted cubic structure and f) system iii - $[ZrX_3]^{-2}$ with the cell geometry and atomic positions fixed at those from the relaxed DP phase of $AZrX_3$

FIG. S4. Total and partial density of states projected over X (S, Se) and A (Sr, Ca) atoms for sulphides and selenides in a) system i - neutral cubic structure $[\text{ZrX}_3]^0$ with no A cation, b) system ii - a hypothetical system $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ with undistorted cubic structure, c) system iii - $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ with the cell geometry and atomic positions fixed at those from the relaxed DP phase of AZrX_3 , d) system iv - cubic $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ structure with a cell volume of 790.8 \AA^3 obtained from unconstrained relaxation leads distorted structure, e) system v - cubic AZrX_3 with the cell volume 498.8 \AA^3 and f) system vi - relaxed distorted structure of AZrX_3

FIG. S5. Comparison of COHP (Crystal Orbital Hamilton Population) projected to nearest neighbour S-S (left panel) and Se-Se (right panel) distances between a) neutral cubic structure of $[\text{ZrX}_3]^0$ and $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ charged system, b) C and DP structure of $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ charged system, c) fixed and relaxed volume DP phase of $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$, d) $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ charged system and SrZrS_3 for sulphides and CaZrSe_3 for selenides in C phase and e) $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ charged system and SrZrS_3 for sulphides and CaZrSe_3 for selenides in DP phase. Note that B and A on y-axis stands for bonding and anti-bonding regions.

FIG. S6. Comparison of COHP (Crystal Orbital Hamilton Population) projected to nearest neighbour Zr-Si(left panel) and Zr-Se (right panel) between a) neutral cubic structure of $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{10}$ and $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ charged system, b) C and DP structure of $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ charged system, c) fixed and relaxed volume DP phase of $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$, d) $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ charged system and SrZrS_3 for sulphides and CaZrSe_3 for selenides in C phase and e) $[\text{ZrX}_3]^{-2}$ charged system and SrZrS_3 for sulphides and CaZrSe_3 for selenides in DP phase. Note that B and A on y-axis stands for bonding and anti-bonding regions.

SIV. THERMAL EFFECTS ON CRYSTAL STRUCTURE

FIG. S7. Variation of linear lattice (α_a , α_b , and α_c) and volume (α_v) thermal expansion coefficients of the DP phase of AZrX₃ (A=Ba, Sr, Ca; X=S, Se) in the temperature range 0-1200 K.

FIG. S8. Radial distribution function for the Zr-S ($\text{RDF}_{\text{Zr-S}}$) and Zr-Se ($\text{RDF}_{\text{Zr-Se}}$) pairs in the DP/C phases of AZrX_3 (A=Ba, Sr, Ca; X=S, Se) at various temperatures.

FIG. S9. Radial distribution function for the A-X atomic pairs in the DP/C phases of AZrX_3 (A=Ba, Sr, Ca; X=S, Se) in the temperature range 300-1200 K.

SV. OBTAINING HSE06 BANDGAPS

The HSE06 calculations are extremely time-consuming compared to those performed at the PBE level, making them impractical to obtain the recalculation of E_g for all configurations for all compositions at all temperatures. However, as reported previously [S3], the HSE06 and PBE+D3 values of E_g in SrZrS_3 are strongly linearly correlated. The linear correlation between HSE06 and PBE+D3 values is also observed for all compositions of AZrX_3 (A=Ba, Sr, Ca; X=S, Se) as demonstrated for temperatures 300 K and 1200 K in Fig. S10. Using this to our advantage, we performed only 20–40 explicit E_g calculations at the HSE06 level for each temperature and performing linear regression, we predicted the HSE06 E_g values for all 200 configurations used in the PBE+D3 calculations to determine the ensemble average.

The HSE06 calculations on chosen configurations were only performed at extreme temperatures, 300 K and 1200 K, for all compositions given the limitations of computing power and time frame. The averages for HSE06 bandgaps for the remaining intermediate temperatures were obtained by using linear regression model obtained from these two data points. The proposed scheme is validated on our prototype structure of SrZrS_3 for which HSE06 bandgaps have been explicitly calculated at all temperatures for PBE functional (without incorporating VdW interactions) as reported in [S3]. The comparison between the calculated bandgaps and the values obtained using the linear model can be clearly observed in Fig. S11. The close overlap of the two values with a negligible difference of ≤ 0.01 eV justifies the proposed approach of obtaining temperature dependent HSE-06 bandgaps, thus making it feasible in limited time frame.

FIG. S10. Linear correlation between electronic bandgaps (E_g) calculated with PBE and HSE06 functional for $AZrX_3$ (A=Ba, Sr, Ca; X=S, Se) at temperatures 300 K and 1200 K.

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FIG. S11. Comparison of calculated HSE-06 bandgaps for the DP phase of SrZrS_3 (PBE method - ref [S3]) against the values calculated using model obtained from linear regression of endpoints at 300 K and 1200 K. The two set of values closely overlap with a difference of less than 0.01 eV.